

Disease Prediction Accuracy in the Healthcare using SVM based machine learning

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Abstract: - One of the major threats to human health today is DM. Diabetes is a metabolic disease where a person suffers from increased sugar levels because either the pancreas does not produce sufficient insulin for the body or the cells do not respond to the insulin. Persistent Diabetes leads to malfunction, injury and failure of organs such as kidneys, eyes, nerves, blood vessels and heart.

The clinical data includes several tests needed to diagnose Diabetes mellitus, depending upon the healthcare personal experience. Hence, it is essential to predict the symptoms of Diabetes at its beginning stage to prevent its growth with appropriate medical diagnosis. These symptoms need to be wisely classified for early detection of Diabetes. The total Diagnosis diabetes dataset is 1094. All datasets applied to the SVM ML technique are divided into two groups. The first group consists of 700 datasets belonging to non-Diabetes, and the second group includes 394 datasets of Diabetes. Hence, the design of a SVM classifier is essential for detecting Diabetes disease with optimal cost and better performance.

Keywords— Diabetes Mellitus (DM), Machine Learning (ML), Support Vector Machine (SVM)

I. INTRODUCTION

In several countries including United States, China, UK healthcare is a thriving domain that has industrialized as a leading sector related to economic growth and employment as well as functional overheads. From the study of the global spending on healthcare, it is anticipated that the general healthcare expenditure will reach double in the following 5 years [1, 2]. In India, public health spending is expected to increase to ₹486000 crores by 2022 from ₹267000 crores in the year 2018. The overall financial outlay to health and wellbeing is expected to rise 45% from the financial year 2018 to 2022. Non-value added and unproductive activities including diagnostic and medication errors, improper usage of antibiotics, readmissions, and deception create a substantial amount of spending for care. Approximately, 5.2 million Indians demise annually due to clinical faults and the consequences of malicious activities [3].

A suitable Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) can handle these problems and accelerate the transformation towards a value-based clinical system to deliver passable care and high services [4]. Digital therapeutics has been recognized to be a renowned intervention for treatment in disease control, and both medical professionals and patients are benefitting from CDSS. At present, the healthcare industry is adopting information and communication technologies for its organizational

venture to deliver high-quality care services in both commercial and technical aspects [5].

DM has developed as a long-term deadly disease across the world and especially in developing nations. Several worldwide and nationwide epidemiological studies have observed the increasing number of diabetics across the globe. Recently, a study exposed that around 463 million individuals between the ages of 20 and 79 years are diabetic patients and it is projected that 552 million people are expected to get affected by the year 2030 [6]. Besides, DM is considered the 5th leading cause of disease-oriented demises and is claimed to cause one death in every 6 seconds globally [7]. Unfortunately, 46.5% of DM patients have not been identified.

Worldwide around 422 million people suffers from diabetes. Diabetes mellitus can be understood to dissimilar types, first category being Type 1 diabetes and the other one being Type 2 diabetes [5, 6]. For case of about all the diabetes cases about 5 to 10% of cases have only the Diabetes – “Type1”. The Diabetes - “Type 2” is about remaining 90% from all the aroused cases. The type-1 diabetes occurs to often kids or adults or during their adolescence days which is caused by the partial dis-functioning of the Pancreas. It will not show any symptoms at the beginning stage because the Pancreas will be functioning partially [7].

II. DIABETS MELLITUS OCCURS

Digestion is a process which requires food to be broken down into various forms of energy or sources of nutrients. Carbohydrates being taken by our body get converted into glucose by our body. Now, we have glucose present in the body which needs insulin to reach to its final destination i.e. the cells within the body so that which helps in building tissues and muscles.

Figure 1: Comparison of death rate of diabetes among different classes of people

Pancreas which are present behind our stomach are responsible for making insulin. When the insulin is released into the blood, glucose enters into the blood by the body cells. If someone, has diabetes then this may be possible due to the various reasons listed below: Pancreases are unable to form the enough amount of insulin required. When the pancreas forms the required amount of insulin, but the beta cells present in the blood does not retaliate to the production thus leaving it in the blood. Thus, Glucose remains unabsorbed thus allowing it to rise beyond levels [8].

Type 1 and 2 are the chronic diabetes problems since it can't be reversed, but gestational and pre-diabetic condition can be reversed. Many health complications may arise due to the diabetes. It is also known as silent killer. In the pandemic times also, people with the diabetes were the most affected ones [11].

Figure 1.1 shows the death caused by diabetes in different categories. A Life – threatening complication of diabetes mellitus can be Diabetic Ketoacidosis or Hyperosmolar Hyperglycemic state. Diabetic Ketoacidosis: Pain in abdomen, severe vomiting, too much urination, unconsciousness is some of the symptoms of ketoacidosis. Sometimes, there is a fruity smell developed in person's breath. Treatment of Ketoacidosis includes the high amount of fluids and insulin injected in the blood. Hyperosmolar hyperglycemic State: When there is too much of blood sugar present, high osmolality can occur in person. Infections, trauma and stroke are one of the few symptoms of the hyperglycemic state [9, 10]. Diabetes can be hazardous, if not predicted in a timely manner, and if predicted on time, but is not being taken care. When insulin is produced in fewer amounts, it highly affects. If it does not receive the proper medication, other body organs such as kidneys, eyes, cardiac system, and nervous system can be majorly affected. Sometime, there is an organ failure leading to death also.

III. ML TECHNIQUE: FUTURE FOR DIABETES CARE

There has been a colossal impact in the healthcare sector with the proliferation of cutting-edge technologies including AI, DM, ML etc. These techniques have demonstrated their effectiveness in disease prediction from massive amounts of healthcare data [11]. They are used to perform prognostic modeling, that is, the exploitation of data and statistics to calculate imminent results from past experiences.

Efficient ML approaches have been employed to develop algorithms in order to support frameworks in diagnosing diabetes in early-stage or its subsequent complications. ML enables a constant and problem-free system for monitoring biomarkers and symptoms. Several ML approaches have been proposed, including unsupervised, supervised, and reinforcement learning approaches. This is obviously practical because ML techniques are driven by data. Since the huge volume of big disease-related data fed into the diagnosis system, ML can save substantial human effort. In the ML approach, models are trained on this data and deliver the more accurate

output according to the input data. Some might analyze features of clinical scans, whereas others use blood test data collected from patients. Because there are several signs of the disease, the parameters differ accordingly. With several established techniques, investigators have investigated different algorithms and tweaked many hyper parameters to achieve outcomes that seem most appropriate for real-time applications.

Many already existing methods are not so effective in diagnosis or prediction. Enough data collected by various healthcare organizations for the decision making for diabetes mellitus. Several new models are used in early diabetes prediction nowadays such as the classifiers of machine learning systems, In-order to get the biomedical statistics various data mining methods used for prediction of the disease [12]. The process of analyzing and collecting various databases and extracting important chunk of data which is used for the effective analysis is known as the Data mining technique. In the diabetic field, predictive analytics method is being used for diagnosis, prediction, self-management, and prevention being done. In the recent trend, the research analysis helps in the diabetes prediction that plays a vigorous role in the case of High mortality and high morbidity, disease compilation and prevention.

Numerous researchers and clinicians have intensified efforts to increase classification performance to achieve superior results when detecting or diagnosing DM. Due to its strong potential to distinguish the _inherent features of different classes of data samples SVM is frequently employed ML technique for the classification of DM [13, 14].

The SVM-based classification includes two phases including learning and testing. In the learning phase, this classification algorithm detects the predictive features by training data samples. During the testing process, the system classifies the newly arrived data sample according to those features and labels them to the equivalent category.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

It offers an automated DM prediction system based on ML methods. With the proper scenario of training and validation, machine learning offers a dependable and great assistance for DM prediction. DM detection requires significant assistance from ML classifiers to identify the illness at a preliminary phase, as it cannot be treated, posing significant complications for our health system. This study aided in the development of a classification system for DM prediction.

Diabetes is gradually becoming one amongst leading causes of chronic infections, with prevalence expected to almost double from 1.5 million over 3.5 million for next two decades if no further measures are taken to combat the disease. Furthermore, some analysis has been conducted on illnesses that often result in misdiagnosis as well as an elevated mortality rate of approximately 98,000 individuals each year as a result of this medical mistake. Left and right data are not evenly distributed. Some of them are also on the right. In reality, may find not many qualities that compare to outrageous cases i.e.,

exemptions. Outliers are the name given to these exceptions. Outliers can be identified and ignored by SVM.

Figure 2: SVM

SVM will automatically ignore these when choosing a hyperplane and choose the best-performing one instead is represent in figure 2.

Import the entire important package

```
#loading dataset
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
#visualisation
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
import seaborn as sns
#EDA
from collections import Counter
import pandas_profiling as pp
# data preprocessing
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
# data splitting
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler # for scaling
from sklearn.pipeline import make_pipeline # for create classifier with prepro
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier, plot_tree # for building mode
#l and draw (plot) tree
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score, train_test_split # for cross validation, and splitting dataset
```

Import the entire model command

```
[ ] from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from xgboost import XGBClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.svm import SVC
#ensembling
from mlxtend.classifier import StackingCvClassifier
```

Upload data for Diabetes

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()

#data.head()

Choose Files No file chosen Upload widget is only available when the cell has been executed in the current browser session. Please rerun this cell to enable.
```

Histogram plot for Attribute

```
# plot histograms for each variable
data.hist(figsize = (12, 12))
plt.show()
```

```
plt.figure(figsize=(10,10))
sns.heatmap(data.corr(),annot=True,fmt='.1f')
plt.show()
```

Classification Technique

```
[ ] m7 = 'Support Vector Classifier'
svc = SVC(kernel='rbf', C=2)
svc.fit(X_train, y_train)
svc_predicted = svc.predict(X_test)
svc_conf_matrix = confusion_matrix(y_test, svc_predicted)
svc_acc_score = accuracy_score(y_test, svc_predicted)
print("confussion matrix")
print(svc_conf_matrix)
print("\n")
print("Accuracy of Support Vector Classifier:",svc_acc_score*100,'\n')
#ax=sns.heatmap(svc_conf_matrix, annot=True, cmap='Blues')
ax.xaxis.set_ticklabels(['False', 'True'])
ax.yaxis.set_ticklabels(['False', 'True'])
plt.show()
```

Confusion Matrix

```
cf_matrix = confusion_matrix(y_test, lr_predict)
print(lr_conf_matrix)
group_names = ["True Neg", "False Pos", "False Neg", "True Pos"]

group_counts = ["{:0.0f}".format(value) for value in cf_matrix.flatten()]
group_percentages = ["{:0.2%}".format(value) for value in cf_matrix.flatten()/np.sum(cf_matrix)]
labels = [{"v1"}\n{v2}\n{v3}" for v1, v2, v3 in zip(group_names,group_counts,group_percentages)]
labels = np.asarray(labels).reshape(2,2)
sns.heatmap(cf_matrix, annot=labels, fmt='', cmap='Blues')
```

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Machine Learning is a thought that agrees over the machine to take data from instances and former knowledge, and learn from historic data to make predictions based on the learning of the past data and that too without being programmed by any programmer i.e.

Figure 3: Histogram of Dataset

ML algorithms are trained by using a training data set for model creation. When some new input data from the attributes is feed to the algorithm of machine learning, prediction is done on the basis of the selected model is shown in figure 3 & figure 4.

Figure 4: Bar Plot of the Number of Diabetes Frequency for Ages

Figure 5: Bar Plot According to Outcomes

In proposed demonstrating at least two related however unique scientific models are utilized and produce their outcomes are joined into a solitary score. Subsequent to playing out the ML approach for testing and preparing we find that exactness of the Inclination supporting is much proficient when contrasted with different calculations. Precision ought to be determined fully backed by disarray framework of every calculation, here number of counts of T.P., TN, F.P., F.N. are given and utilizing the condition of precision, esteem has been determined and it is presume that proposed calculation is best among them with 93.67% exactness and the correlation is displayed in Table 1. And graphical represent in fig. 6.

Table 1: Simulation Parameter

Design	Precision	Recall	Accuracy
Previous Design	89.45%	91.49%	89.34%
Implemented SVM Design	93.34%	94.82%	93.67%

Figure 6: Graphical Representation

VI. CONCLUSION

Due to the fact that diabetes is the root cause of numerous diseases in the human body, it is essential to detect this serious condition as soon as possible. There have been a number of approaches taken in the past to make it easier for doctors to diagnose diabetes. However, there is a classification issue with it: a selection of an excessive number of samples, but it does not improve classification accuracy. The speed of the algorithm is better in a few situations, but the accuracy of the data classification is lower. As can be seen, the majority model employs previous and SVM classifiers and its accuracy for the diabetes disease dataset is 89.34%, and 93.67%, respectively.

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